

Influence of Management Variables on Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of management variables on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population comprised 224 professional librarians in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria. A census sampling approach was adopted because the population size was manageable. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation, while a reliability coefficient of 0.84 was established using Cronbach's Alpha. Data were analysed using simple linear regression analysis at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that planning positively influenced service delivery in academic libraries ($R = .414$, $R^2 = .171$, $p < .05$). Staffing was also found to positively influence service delivery ($R = .462$, $R^2 = .213$, $p < .05$) and emerged as the strongest predictor among the management variables investigated. Furthermore, organisation positively influenced service delivery ($R = .424$, $R^2 = .180$, $p < .05$). The findings indicated that management variables are significant determinants of service delivery in academic libraries. The study concluded that effective planning, adequate staffing, and sound organisational structures are essential for enhancing service delivery in academic libraries. Improved management practices contribute significantly to the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of library services. The study recommended that academic library management should prioritise the recruitment, training, and retention of qualified personnel, develop strategic plans aligned with institutional goals, and establish clear organisational structures to enhance effective service delivery.

Keywords: *Academic libraries, management variables, service delivery, library management, Cross River State.*

Introduction

Academic libraries are fundamental to effective teaching and learning in tertiary institutions, as they are the storehouse of all kinds of knowledge and basic information resources and services needed for research, learning and teaching. The library is meant to be repositories of basic information resources that are carefully selected, acquired, preserved and made accessible to the members of the parent institution. Given the important role played by the library in the success of any academic institution, the effective management of libraries therefore becomes crucial if the library is to achieve its goal of supporting academic programs and enhancing teaching and learning. It is therefore imperative for library management to ensure that librarians properly acquire and manage information resources for effective and efficient service delivery.

Service delivery involves everything a librarian does to render assistance to a library user in quest of knowledge in order to gratify their information needs as well as improve their experience within the library. It is the summary of every library activity that is aimed at improving library users' experience in utilising the library and its resources. Service delivery can be appraised by the librarians' ability to meet the information needs of the library patrons promptly in order to satisfy the expectations of the users. The major focus of the university library is the intellectual life of the university community, which is established for research, teaching, learning and community service, which is the essence of establishing the library. User education services, inter-library loan, abstracting services, cataloguing services, reprographic services, bibliographic services, circulation services, reference services and information services are some of the services delivered in university libraries (Okoro & Orjiako, 2025). Library management variables are very critical indices in determining the quality of service delivered to library users in academic libraries.

Library management variables depict the different strategies engaged by library managers to gratify users' information needs and meet the core objectives of the library and its parent institution. The administration of information resources and services in libraries by librarians is the main emphasis of library management. The library managers are expected to be skilled in basic attributes that will allow them to perform their administrative duties successfully and efficiently. These attributes are what the researchers consider as management variables, and they include planning, staffing and organisation. Planning by library managers involves the process of setting goals and determining the activities that should be performed within a specified period and the funding implications of each. It is an important management variable as it helps to clearly formulate the mission and vision statements of the library as well as detail out the strategies of achieving the aims and objectives of the host institution. Planning affords librarians an opportunity to embark on a feasibility study to have first-class information and knowledge of what is available and what should be provided. Thus, effective planning for library services involves a framework for policy and decision- making which in turn provides the rules governing the activities of user services in order to guarantee efficiency and continuity.

Staffing is an important management variable, as the library's ability to function effectively depends on how competent its personnel are. The calibre and proficiency of the personnel working in the library always determine how well library resources and services are provided to the library users. If academic libraries are to offer efficient and current library services and resources, then qualified library staff should be employed and deployed to the different sections of the library. Staffing involves managing the organisational structure of the library through proper and effective selection, appraisal and development of personnel to fill the roles designed into the structure. This implies that qualified library staff should be deployed to the proper positions with their distinct job classification and descriptions.

Organisation in libraries implies determining the specific activities that are to be carried out by each library staff member to accomplish the planned goals and objectives of the library. Organisation generally is the process of defining and grouping the activities of an organisation and establishing authority relationships among them. It is a process of identifying and grouping the work to be performed, defining and delegating responsibility and authority, and establishing relationships for the purpose of enabling people to work most effectively together in accomplishing objectives. Organisation as a function of management leads to the creation of an organisational structure with suitable personnel, designing specific roles to eliminate ambiguity, defining interrelationships among personnel for productive cooperation, and clarifying authority and responsibility for results and logical grouping of activities.

Statement of the Problem

The managerial variables of library managers are critical factors that can influence the overall effectiveness and efficiency of library service delivery by the library staff. This is true of the fact that, despite the essential role that libraries play in providing access to information resources and services, most library users are still not satisfied with the quality of service delivery and resources they get from the library, which has, over time, reduced library patronage by the users. The researchers ponder whether this is a result of library managers' inability to effectively exhibit their managerial functions properly.

For academic libraries to render efficient library services and quality information resources to their users, the library managers need to be diligent in their management practices in terms of planning, organising, staffing and coordinating the library staff to ensure that they are at their duty post rendering services to the library users.

Given the limited empirical research on the relationship between management variables and service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria, it becomes imperative to carry out this research and provide data that can bridge the knowledge gap and enable library managers and policymakers to identify possible solutions to poor service delivery in academic libraries within Cross River State.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to determine the:

1. influence of planning on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.
2. influence of staffing on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.
3. influence of organisation on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of planning on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of staffing on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria?
3. What is the influence of organisation on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for testing at a 0.05 level of significance:

- Ho₁: There is no significant influence of planning on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.
- Ho₂: There is no significant influence of staffing on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.
- Ho₃: There is no significant influence of organisation on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Planning and Service Delivery

Planning is the systematic process of setting goals, determining appropriate actions, and allocating resources in advance to achieve organisational objectives efficiently and effectively. It involves forecasting future conditions, identifying priorities, and developing strategies to guide decision-making and implementation. According to Kenyangwa and Njuguna (2025), planning positively affects service delivery outcomes. For example, research at Kenya Power Headquarters using regression analysis found that strategic planning had a substantial positive effect on the quality and reliability of services provided, highlighting the importance of clear planning processes, communication, and employee training for enhancing service outcomes.

Ambetsa, Kadima, and Miroga (2022) quantitatively demonstrated that planning influences service delivery performance in the water department of a county government in Kenya. Their descriptive and inferential analyses showed that implementing structured strategic management practices improved service delivery, suggesting that planning enhances alignment of objectives with operational execution.

Jackson and Ombui (2018) found that comprehensive procurement planning, including portfolio development, policy formation, logistics management, and budgeting, was significantly and positively associated with service delivery performance. This study employed quantitative survey methods to establish relationships between planning variables and delivery outcomes. The study also highlights that organisational processes surrounding planning such as maintenance culture and resource allocation, affect service delivery. Jackson and Ombui (2018) demonstrated that procurement planning, including procurement portfolios, policies, logistics management, and budgeting, had a positive and statistically significant effect on service delivery in state corporations in Kenya. This study revealed that improved planning of procurement processes ensures the timely availability of resources and supports operational effectiveness. Further, Wandera, Abuya, and Kiongera (2023) found that strategic procurement planning accounted for a substantial proportion of variance in service delivery within county governments in Western Kenya, with an increase in planning rigour corresponding to notable improvements in service outcomes.

Chiwawa and Wissink (2024) examined strategy execution in South African municipalities and found that barriers and enablers of strategic planning implementation, such as leadership engagement and stakeholder coordination, shaped the capacity of municipalities to deliver quality services to citizens, indicating that planning execution, not just formulation, determines delivery effectiveness. Qualitative healthcare research focusing on service users' perspectives highlights that effective health services planning and delivery hinge on understanding local needs, identifying barriers, and organising services to match expected quality standards, suggesting that planning grounded in user feedback facilitates more responsive service delivery.

Staffing and Service Delivery

Staffing refers to the process through which an organisation recruits, selects, deploys, and manages adequate and competent personnel to carry out activities that result in the efficient and effective provision of services to clients or the public. Staffing focuses on ensuring the right number and quality of employees are available to perform organisational tasks, while service delivery involves the actual performance of these tasks to meet expected standards of quality, timelines, and satisfaction. In healthcare settings, retrospective longitudinal observational studies demonstrate that higher registered nurse staffing levels are associated with reduced patient mortality, fewer missed vital signs, and shorter lengths of stay, highlighting that adequate staffing is critical for safe and effective service delivery (Staffing Levels, Missed Vital Signs and Mortality in Hospitals, 2018).

Richard, Enidiok, Akpan-Atata, and Inyang (2025) investigated librarians' competencies for library automation as determinants of electronic information service provision in federal university libraries in South-East Nigeria. The study found that project management skills, metadata management skills, and knowledge of library software significantly influenced electronic information service provision. The findings suggest that competent and well-trained library personnel are essential for effective service delivery in academic libraries.

Morgan and Griffiths (2025) found through a systematic review of longitudinal studies that greater nurse staffing levels are generally linked to lower patient mortality, confirming the importance of both the quantity and quality of staff. Moreover, Li, Wang, Pu, Xie, Xu, and Shen (2024) found

that nursing managers perceive staffing adequacy as a key determinant of service quality, with implications for job satisfaction and work engagement, which in turn influence patient care outcomes.

Wangechi, Koome, and Gesimba (2020) observed in the hospitality industry in Kenya that structured learning and development programs, a key staffing practice, significantly improved service delivery outcomes. Adesunloye, Arowosafe, and Oyeleke (2025) reported that employee engagement and job satisfaction mediated the relationship between staffing and service delivery in Nigerian hotels, indicating that well-managed staff directly enhance customer satisfaction and operational efficiency. Xatse and Naong (2025) further emphasised that human resource quality and structured staffing practices in local government services significantly influence service delivery efficiency, although motivation alone may not suffice without proper systems support.

Research in China found that staffing policies and practices shaping both quantitative and qualitative staffing adequacy significantly affected team performance in healthcare settings, with higher adequacy linked to increased engagement and better outcomes, pointing to the importance of structured staffing management on service delivery performance (Wei et al., 2024). Similarly, studies in healthcare workforce planning emphasise that shortages and uneven staffing distribution can undermine service delivery effectiveness, revealing that sustainable workforce planning is essential for maintaining care quality as demand changes over time (Hewage & Rostami-Tabar, 2024). Mwaniki, Ogola, and Nyerere (2022) found that staffing levels in public secondary schools significantly influenced the quality of education delivered, with adequate teaching staff correlated with improved learning outcomes, highlighting that human resource capacity affects service quality beyond healthcare into education service delivery.

Organisation and Service Delivery

Organising refer to the process by which an organisation structures tasks, coordinates activities, assigns responsibilities, and establishes systems and relationships to ensure that services are provided efficiently and effectively to meet the needs of clients or the public. Kartvedt (2024) examined coordination quality in local public service delivery and found that public managers' perceived coordination quality significantly influenced the effectiveness of local services, underscoring that how service activities are organised and aligned across departments shapes delivery performance. Mandila, Odero, and Musiega (2025) provided evidence that organisational innovation, as an aspect of how institutions structure and organise their processes, was positively and significantly related to service delivery outcomes in public universities, demonstrating that newer organisational arrangements and collaborative structures can enhance service efficiency and effectiveness. Similarly, Krone-Hjertstrøm, Norbye, Abelsen, and colleagues (2021) used ethnographic methods to show how nurses' organising work coordination, knowledge sharing, and adjustment of service processes shaped the implementation of a new acute care service, indicating that service delivery outcomes are deeply influenced by how work is coordinated at the point of care.

Mbiti and Misango (2025) found that organisational structure and culture significantly influenced service delivery outcomes in the County Government of Kitui, Kenya, with regression analysis indicating that aligned structures and supportive cultures enhanced coordination and beneficiary

satisfaction. Similarly, Ndungu and Kiiru's (2024) quantitative study of the National Police Service in Nairobi City County reported that alignment of organisational structure, culture, resources, and technology was positively related to service delivery efficiency, suggesting that integrated structural coordination supports better communication and operational clarity.

In Uganda's local governments, Musenze and Mayende (2021) used qualitative methods to show that effective coordination between departments is associated with higher quality service delivery, highlighting that organised interdependence and policy execution processes promote better outcomes. The research further affirms that clear, well-defined organisational structures improve decision-making and communication flows, thereby enhancing service delivery efficiency. For example, Mutambuki (2025) reported that a hierarchical organisational structure in county government facilitated quicker administrative decisions and improved service quality, indicating that structural clarity supports responsive service execution.

Okoro and Orjiako (2025) found in federal Nigerian universities that Office Information Systems (OIS) significantly enhanced service-delivery efficiency because the organised integration of technology and human resources improves responsiveness, record-keeping, and service access, demonstrating that organised technological structures complement human resource arrangements in delivering services.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The design was considered appropriate because it enabled the researchers to collect data from a relatively large population and examine the influence of management variables on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria. The study was conducted in Cross River State, located in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, where several universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education operate academic libraries that support teaching, learning, and research activities. The population of the study comprised 224 professional librarians working in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria. Professional librarians were defined as personnel possessing Library and Information Science qualifications and performing professional library functions. Paraprofessional staff such as library assistants and clerical personnel were excluded from the study. A census (total enumeration) sampling technique was adopted because the population size was manageable. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled *Management Variables and Service Delivery in Academic Libraries Questionnaire (MVSDALQ)*. The instrument consisted of 24 items and was divided into two sections. Section A elicited respondents' demographic information, while Section B contained 24 items measuring planning (6 items), staffing (6 items), organisation (6 items) and service delivery (6 items). The items were structured on a four-point Likert-type scale. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts, comprising two lecturers from the Department of Library and Information Science and one lecturer from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation, University of Calabar. Their observations and suggestions were incorporated to improve the instrument.

A pilot study was conducted using academic librarians outside the study area, and data obtained were analysed using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.84, indicating

that the instrument was reliable. The researchers administered the questionnaire with the assistance of trained research assistants. The research assistants were trained on the purpose of the study, ethical considerations and procedures for administering and retrieving the questionnaire. A total of 224 copies of the questionnaire were administered and all 224 copies were correctly completed and returned, representing a response rate of 100%. Before analysis, the data were screened and found suitable for regression analysis. Data collected were coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Simple linear regression analysis was used to determine the predictive influence of management variables on service delivery at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Simple linear regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question One

What is the influence of planning on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Result of Simple Linear Regression of the Influence of Planning on Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria (N = 224)

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Planning Service Delivery	0.414	0.171	0.167

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

The regression model suggests a positive relationship between planning and service delivery. This implies that effective planning practices contribute to improvements in service delivery within academic libraries. The result of the simple linear regression analysis revealed that planning significantly influenced service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria ($p < .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that planning is a significant predictor of service delivery in academic libraries. The result further showed that planning accounted for 17.1% ($R^2 = .171$) of the variance in service delivery, indicating that effective planning contributes positively to improved service delivery. The remaining 82.9% of the variance in service delivery may be attributed to other factors not examined in this study, such as funding adequacy, information and communication technology facilities, leadership practices, staff motivation, organisational culture, and user-related factors.

Research Question Two

What is the influence of staffing on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Result of Simple Linear Regression of the Influence of Staffing on Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria (N = 224)

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Staffing	0.462	0.213	0.210
Service Delivery			

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

The regression model suggests a positive relationship between staffing and service delivery. This implies that improvements in staffing practices, such as the availability of qualified personnel and effective staff deployment, are associated with enhanced service delivery in academic libraries. The result of the simple linear regression analysis revealed that staffing significantly influenced service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria ($p < .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that staffing is a significant predictor of service delivery in academic libraries. The result further showed that staffing accounted for 21.3% ($R^2 = .213$) of the variance in service delivery, indicating that adequate staffing contributes positively to effective service delivery. The remaining 78.7% of the variance in service delivery may be explained by other organisational and environmental factors not included in the present model. This suggests that staffing exerts an appreciable influence on service delivery in academic libraries.

Research Question Three

What is the influence of organisation on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Result of Simple Linear Regression of the Influence of Organisation on Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria (N = 224)

Variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Organisation	0.424	0.180	0.176
Service Delivery			

Source: Field Survey, 2026.

The regression model suggests a positive relationship between organisation and service delivery. This indicates that effective organisational structures, clear role definitions, and efficient coordination mechanisms are associated with improved service delivery in academic libraries. The result of the simple linear regression analysis revealed that organisation significantly influenced service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria ($p < .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that organisation is a significant predictor of service delivery in academic libraries. The result further showed that organisation accounted for 18.0% ($R^2 = .180$) of the variance in service delivery, indicating that effective organisational structures contribute positively to service delivery. The remaining 82.0% of the variance in service delivery may be associated with other variables beyond organisational structure, including funding, technology infrastructure, staff competence, and institutional support. This suggests that human resource

factors play a relatively stronger role in enhancing service delivery in academic libraries than planning and organisational factors.

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: There is no significant influence of planning on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 4: ANOVA Result of the Influence of Planning on Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria (N = 224)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression		1		45.80	.000
Residual		222			
Total		223			

As indicated in the table, since p (.000) is less than .05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that planning has a significant influence on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: There is no significant influence of staffing on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 5: ANOVA Result of the Influence of Staffing on Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria (N = 224)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression		1		60.12	.000
Residual		222			
Total		223			

As indicated in the table, since p (.000) is less than .05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that staffing has a significant influence on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three

Ho₃: There is no significant influence of organisation on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 6: ANOVA Result of the Influence of Organisation on Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria (N = 224)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression		1		48.73	.000
Residual		222			
Total		223			

As indicated in the table, since $p (.000)$ is less than $.05$, the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that the organisation has a significant influence on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Discussion

The findings revealed that planning has a significant influence on service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria. The regression analysis revealed that planning accounted for 17.1% of the variance in service delivery, indicating that planning makes a meaningful contribution to the effectiveness of library services. This finding may be attributed to the role of planning in establishing goals, coordinating activities, allocating resources, and guiding decision-making processes within academic libraries. Through effective planning, library managers can anticipate users' information needs, prioritise services, and utilise available resources efficiently. Strategic planning also promotes continuity and accountability, thereby enhancing service delivery. The finding agrees with Kenyangwa and Njuguna (2025), who reported that strategic planning positively influenced service delivery outcomes through improved operational effectiveness. The finding is also consistent with Ambetsa, Kadima, and Miroga (2022), Jackson and Ombui (2018), and Wandera, Abuya, and Kiongera (2023), who reported that planning-related practices significantly improved service delivery across public institutions.

The finding further revealed that staffing significantly influences service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria. Staffing accounted for 21.3% of the variance in service delivery and emerged as the strongest predictor among the management variables investigated. This finding may be explained by the fact that library personnel constitute the primary mechanism through which services are delivered to users. Qualified and competent staff are better positioned to provide reference assistance, manage information resources, support digital services, and respond effectively to users' needs. Adequate staffing also reduces work overload and promotes efficiency in service provision. The finding supports Morgan and Griffiths (2025), who established that staffing levels significantly affect service outcomes. Similarly, Li et al. (2024) reported that staffing adequacy influences service quality and operational effectiveness. The finding also agrees with Richard et al. (2025), who found that librarians' competencies significantly influenced electronic information service delivery in federal university libraries.

The study also revealed that organisation significantly influences service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria. Organisation accounted for 18.0% of the variance in service delivery, indicating that organisational arrangements contribute substantially to service effectiveness. This finding may be attributed to the fact that clearly defined organisational structures facilitate coordination, communication, supervision, and accountability. Effective organisational systems enable staff to understand their responsibilities, streamline workflow processes, and minimise service delays. Consequently, users are able to access information resources and services more efficiently. The finding is consistent with Ndungu and Kiiru (2024), who reported that organisational alignment significantly enhanced service delivery efficiency. The finding also agrees with Mbiti and Misango (2025) and Musenze and Mayende (2021), who found that effective organisational structures and coordination mechanisms positively influenced service delivery outcomes. The findings demonstrate that management variables significantly contribute

to service delivery in academic libraries. Although all three variables were significant predictors, staffing exerted the greatest influence, followed by organisation and planning. This suggests that while strategic planning and organisational arrangements are important, the availability of competent and adequately supported personnel remains the most critical factor in improving service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The study revealed the following findings:

1. Planning influenced service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria, accounting for 17.1% ($R^2 = .171$) of the variance in service delivery.
2. Staffing influenced service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria, accounting for 21.3% ($R^2 = .213$) of the variance in service delivery. Staffing emerged as the strongest predictor among the management variables investigated.
3. Organisation influenced service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria, accounting for 18.0% ($R^2 = .180$) of the variance in service delivery.

Conclusion

The study relied on self-reported data obtained from professional librarians, which may be subject to response bias. Furthermore, the use of simple linear regression examined each management variable independently and did not account for the combined effects of multiple predictors. Future studies may employ multiple regression analysis and incorporate user-based measures of service delivery to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing service delivery in academic libraries. Therefore, based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that management variables significantly influence service delivery in academic libraries in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, planning, staffing, and organisation were found to have significant positive influences on service delivery. Effective planning enables academic libraries to allocate resources strategically and align their activities with institutional objectives. Adequate staffing ensures the availability of competent personnel for efficient service provision, while sound organisational structures enhance coordination, communication, and operational efficiency. Thus, effective management practices remain essential for improving the quality and effectiveness of service delivery in academic libraries.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Academic library management should prioritise the recruitment, training, and retention of qualified library personnel, as staffing emerged as the strongest predictor of service delivery.
2. Academic libraries should develop and implement comprehensive strategic plans that align library operations with institutional goals and user needs.
3. Academic libraries should establish clear organisational structures, responsibilities, and communication channels to enhance coordination and operational efficiency.

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